

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY OF POPULATION

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Abstract: *A person can withstand difficulties for years if he can feel the ability to influence the situation, or at least to see it. A person's sense of needing help, feeling weak and powerless is a completely different matter.*

Key words: *Stress, Mental (psychological), Eustress, Distress, Inhibitory type, Anxiety, Fear, Fright, Hadik, Horror, Panic.*

Introduction: The mental state of people in an emergency situation is different. In the initial period, people's reactions are based on the instinct of self-preservation. However, the degree of such reactions is different: from irrational panicked action to purposeful conscious action.

Stress exists in everyone's life, because stress impulses are found in all aspects of human life. Stressful situations occur both at home and at work. Stress is the cause of many diseases, it causes serious damage to human health.

Mental (psychological) preparation is the formation of mental endurance in people or the formation of qualities that strengthen the ability to perform a given task and act selflessly in dangerous situations.

The main tasks of mental (psychological) preparation are as follows;

1. Development of high mental stability in different categories of the population during emergency situations.
2. Cultivate the readiness of every citizen to come to the aid of victims in emergency situations.
3. To ensure that the population has the skills to protect themselves in all emergency situations that are likely to occur.

4. Formation of humaneness and willingness of rescuers to help victims and save them.

5. Formation of high moral qualities among leaders and education of self-confidence and willingness to protect the population from emergency situations.

In the process of activity, the body's reaction to external influences does not remain constant. The organism tries to adapt to the changing conditions of activity. This causes mental stress. Canadian physiologist G. Seele (1936) called this condition stress.

Period of Anxiety: During this period, the natives who remain in the Disaster or natural calamity zone will undoubtedly face more difficulties. According to the results of the conducted researches, 50-75% of the population living in the area where such a situation has arisen have been diagnosed with demonic possession and temptation, and 12-25%. Some people are in a state of strong excitement and perform crazy actions, while others, on the contrary, show stiffness, depression, and indifference to the events happening around them. Only 12-15% of people do not lose their temper and act decisively and rationally in a difficult situation.

- Stress can persist for years and have a negative impact on a person's condition, life satisfaction, and work efficiency. Accumulated stress and overwork lead to delayed consequences. For representatives of the extreme field, a possible consequence of a long-lasting stressful situation or acute stress is the development of occupational disability syndrome, post-traumatic stress disorders.

- Diseases that can be caused by stress:

- In the emotional sphere: the onset of neurosis - a decrease in strong emotions, constant apathy, restlessness, sleep disorders, memory loss, inability to concentrate.

- In the cardiovascular system: tachycardia, heart attack, high blood pressure, vascular spasm, headache, migraine.

- Immune system: decrease in number of lymphocytes, decrease in protective functions.

- Gastrointestinal tract: indigestion, nausea, heartburn, diarrhea and constipation, gastritis, colic inflammation, flatulence, stomach and duodenum wound

- Skin: rashes, itching, fodder, eczema, hives.

- Endocrine system: thyroid dysfunction, diabetes.

- Muscles: overexertion, high risk of trauma.

- It is possible and necessary to develop and strengthen the emotional stability of a person. In addition to psychological preparation for difficulties, danger, sudden complexity of the situation, a person's personal reaction to a strong stress situation and psychological endurance depends on his ideological confidence, worldview, interests, how the issue is posed, duty, responsibility, fraternity.

- Psychologists-scientists also talk about the importance of such preparation. They cite a surprising number: 65% of the fighting ability of military units depends on the psychophysiological state of the soldiers. This fully applies to FVDT structures and units. Often they work in conditions that can be equated with a combat situation.

- The essence of psychological preparation in emergency situations. The word "spiritual" means "pertaining to the inner world of a person." It is a form of social consciousness, a set of principles and standards that people follow when walking, standing, and interacting. These norms are an expression of certain relations of people to each other and to various forms of human unity (family, work team, nation, society as a whole).

- Giving a moral (ethical) assessment to behaviors and their reasons is a unique aspect of spirituality. The concept of good and bad, duty, conscience, dishonesty formed in the society, among a certain stratum of the population, is the basis for such assessment, and the requirements of a certain population stratum of the society to the individual are expressed in these concepts.

Conclusion: There are the following forms of promotion of civil protection:

1. Word of mouth promotion.

2. Mass media (press, television, radio).
3. Movies and videos.
4. Visual aids. (poster, stand, photomontage, showcase, etc.)

Promotion of knowledge in the field of protection of the population and territories from emergency situations using these methods of promotion is provided by state bodies, as well as relevant public associations for the protection and rescue of people. Mass media can be used to promote knowledge.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protection of Population and Territories from Natural and Man-made Emergency Situations" (08.20.1999).
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Civil Protection" (26.05.2000).
3. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the procedure for preparing the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for emergency protection" (No. 754, September 9, 2019).
4. <https://lex.uz/> - visual aids: multimedia program, psychological tests, situation cards.